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Key parameters for the simulation of agrivoltaics in greenhouses with bifacial PV modules

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Lusim: PV simulation tool including GPU-based 3D modelling for complex shading, bifacial gain, agrivoltaics

Typical values of bifacial gain in greenhouses

Bifacial gain values obtained from around 400 simulation cases corresponding to a wide variety of scenarios in greenhouses

Typical bifacial **irradiation** gain: 3% - 8%

Typical bifacial **energy** gain: 2% - 5%

Key parameters influencing PV and crops yield in greenhouses

- Shading from greenhouse structure
- Light transmittance of the greenhouse (glass, PVC, light diffusing coating)
- Photovoltaic modules mounting (Ground Cover Ratio, Orientation, Tilt, Tracking)
- Albedo (Ground, Crops, Environment)
- Crops type and geometry
- Crops growth from incident light (PAR, crops model, other variables)
- Air temperature inside the greenhouse, Temperature of the PV modules

3D modelling of some typical structures of greenhouses

Structural elements blocking the sunlight:

- Vertical supports
- Cross beams
- Mounting racks for PV modules

Key characteristics of structural elements:

- Dimensions
- Shapes
- Density

Shading from greenhouse structures and their impact on bifacial gain

Annual bifacial irradiation gain loss due to greenhouse structure shading

Relative impact of the greenhouse structure shading on bifacial irradiation gain

Typical bifacial irradiation loss due to structures: 1% - 15%

Most corresponding energy yield losses $\leq 0.5\%$

(e.g. if BEG = 5% and structure loss = 10%
 \rightarrow energy yield loss = 5% * 10% = 0.5%)

Higher impact of structures on bifacial gain
 when higher bifacial gain

(because the sunlight cannot be blocked twice)

Greenhouse light transmittance

Challenges for the modelling of light transmittance in greenhouses:

- Light transmittance through different materials (e.g. glass or PVC)
- Spectrally selective transmittance
- Incident Angle Modifier (IAM) losses
- Transmittance greatly affected by soiling (outside and inside the greenhouse)
- Soiling difficult to assess, depends on human activity, and highly seasonal
- Use of light diffusing coating → reduction of light transmittance and complex modelling of diffuse light

Tracking and backtracking in greenhouses can present some specificities

Challenges for the modelling of tracking and backtracking in greenhouses:

- The tracking rotation angles are limited by the structures
- All the PV modules are not always coplanar
- One PV array might cast a shadow on another PV array whose plane of array is different
- The backtracking strategies need to consider two different planes of array

3D modelling of the crops: high spatial resolution approach

Key ideas of the approach

- High spatial resolution 3D modelling of the crops
- Use of high resolution meshes to model the incident and reflected sunlight on each small part of the crops

Pros

- Possibility to take into account many details
- The optical porosity of the crops is directly evaluated

Cons

- Complex
- Computation time consuming
- Needed inputs not always available

3D modelling of the crops: simple geometric shapes approach

Source: Velarde et al., 2018

Key ideas of the approach:

- Represent the crops through simple geometric shapes
- Apply optical properties to these objects (albedo, BRDF, effective light porosity)

Evaluation of the **optical porosity** of the crops in a hemispheric

Modelling of the Albedo / Reflectance

Spectral response of typical PV cells

Source: PVP/MC / PVlib (accessed 2022)

Spectral albedo of typical materials

Source: Russel et al., 2017

Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF)

Spectral albedo and BRDF can lead to deviations of several % from reference broadband albedo values

This deviation might be **negative** (albedo reduction) or **positive** (albedo increase)

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